

GLOBAL ECONOMY CONCEPT: COMPOSITION AND ELEMENTS

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Abstract: the article presents analyzes related to the concept of global economy, its essence, structure and elements. The modern trends of the global economy as a growing process have been studied.

Key words: Globalization, modern trends, economic system, integration, modernization, diversification.

The global economy is a qualitatively new stage in the development of the world economy, which is gradually turning into an integral global system formed by a huge production and trade, global financial and information network on a planetary scale.

Functional elements of the global economy:

1. Globalization of production and global production;
2. Global financial system;
3. Global system of trade of goods and services;
4. Global markets of capital, labor and information technologies;
5. A global system of exchange with the results of intellectual activity.

The process of forming the elements of the global economy is developing simultaneously in several directions. The first of them is the sale of goods and services produced in the domestic market of the country, on the one hand, due to a significant increase in the scale of production and, on the other hand, the saturation of domestic needs in relation to the goods and services of national production. On this basis, there is a need to always look for foreign markets to sell the gross product created in the country in value and natural form. Another direction is its opposite, which requires a large-scale exit to the world market due to the lack of all labor tools and objects that ensure the continuity and expansion of the production process in the national economy.

The following are the specific features of the global economy:

- developed field of international commodity exchange based on international trade;
- developed field of international movement of production factors (capital, labor force, technology);
- forms of international production of enterprises located in several countries;

- an independent international financial sector that is not related to the provision of services for the international movement of goods and production factors;

- the system of international mechanisms of international and interstate, interstate and non-state regulation in order to ensure the balance and stability of economic development;

- Economic policy of the states based on the principles of open economy.

The economy of most countries of the world is becoming more open, which helps them to actively participate in global economic processes and ensures a stable growth trend of the share of goods exports in the world GDP. For example, from 7.9% in 1913. Up to 9% in 1929, 10% in 1960, up to 14.5% in 1970, 19% in 2000, 21.7% in 2018 and in high-income countries - a member of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (European Cooperation and Development Organization) - the share of exports of goods and services (% of GDP) is 70%. The average annual growth rate of export of goods is almost two times higher than GDP growth. This process accelerated the process of international economic integration.

International economic integration can affect national economies in different forms and levels as a result of the effective development of the union of the economies of certain countries and their mutual relations based on the division of labor. International economic integration is a new and at the same time complex stage of the internationalization of economic relations, and it is a point of high, effective and future-oriented development of the world economy. In this case, not only the national economies will be united, but also the solution of economic problems will be provided in cooperation. At this point, it should be said that economic integration as a process leading countries to work together is manifested in the following:

cooperation between national economies of different countries and their complete or partial integration;

- partial or complete elimination of obstacles in the movement of goods, services, capital and labor between countries;

- gradual unification of the markets of certain countries in order to create a single market;

- elimination of differences between economic entities belonging to different countries one after another;

- to prevent discrimination of foreign entities engaged in economic activity in each partner country.

Economic integration processes can be bilateral, multi-country and inter-regional. Nowadays, one of the main issues of integrated associations is to ensure their development at the regional level. In this matter, an interstate management system is usually introduced and a single general regional economic complex is established. At the current stage, consistent changes are taking place in all aspects of the international relations system. Most of it is related to the development of globalization processes.

Globalization is the highest stage of internationalization, and from this point of view it is based not only on the increase in the movement of people and goods, but also on the exchange of knowledge and information.

Globalization is one of the main processes in the development of the modern world economy, and it is a high stage of the internationalization of economic life.

As a result of the development of international division of labor, international production cooperation, foreign trade and other forms of international economic relations, the interconnection and interdependence of national economies is becoming increasingly stronger. Currently, it is impossible to ensure the economic development of countries without taking into account external factors. All countries that are part of the world economy, developed and developing countries, as well as third world countries, are being pulled into the vortex of globalization processes. It is known that the processes of globalization began to be clearly visible in the world economy system in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century. These include, as a result of the concentration and integration of production, its globalization and the emergence of global production, as a result of which the demand for capital and labor resources and financial instruments increases, the migration of capital and labor resources increases, the global system of trade in goods and services and the global financial system led to its formation. As a result of these processes, global markets of capital, labor and information technologies were formed. In general, scientific and technical development (ITT) is the basis of modern globalization processes. The transition of ITT to a new qualitative stage in the second half of the 20th century (scientific and technical revolution) made science the fifth factor of production worldwide, and as a result, the markets of scientific and technical developments were created, and a global system of exchange with the results of intellectual activity was formed. As a result of the international specialization and cooperation of production, the deepening of the division of labor, the internationalization of production and capital led to the expansion of

transnational corporations and the expansion of the scope of large international corporations, as a result of which these processes led to the general liberalization of foreign economic relations and the emergence and development of open national economies.

Today, informatization and information technologies are becoming one of the important aspects of the development of the international economy; The growing desire for interstate regulation of current economic and currency-financial processes at the international level, which is higher than the regulation at the national level, deepens the processes of globalization. As a result, the anti-globalist movement has emerged in order to protect national economic and social interests.

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